

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1 Pigment concentrations over time, measured by HPLC, for nitrogen-depletion and iron-depletion experiments.

C

Centric diatoms

D

Pennate diatoms

Figure S2 Microscopy-based phytoplankton cell counts across conditions (MB1-8). (A) coarse taxonomy; (B) dinoflagellate groups; (C) centric diatom groups; (D) pennate diatom groups, (E) counts of small cells recovered from 0.8 μm filtration.

Figure S4 Phylogenetic tree showing distribution of active eukaryotic taxa from 18S rRNA amplicons (SD 7). Circles representing amplicon abundance are colored by sample origin (MB1-8) and superimposed over a reference phylogeny which is colored by taxonomy. Proximity of circles to the tips of branches represents closeness to references.

Figure S5 Phylogenetic tree showing distribution of active bacterial taxa using 16S rRNA amplicons (SD 9). Circles representing amplicon abundance are colored by sample origin (MB1-8) and superimposed over a reference phylogeny which is colored by taxonomy. Proximity of circles to the tips of branches represents closeness to references.

Figure S6 Structure of the active 16S bacterial community across conditions. Community structure is shown at both a high taxonomic level (A, B) and also within groups (C-J).

Figure S7 Ordination of bacterial rRNA counts shows mid-bloom conditions (MB1, MB3) from the nitrogen-depletion experiment clustering together, late-bloom conditions from the nitrogen-depletion experiment (MB2, MB4) clustering together, and Fe-replete conditions (MB5, MB7) from the iron-depletion experiment clustering together.

**Alexandrium monilatum,
Strain CCMP3105**

Alexandrium temarense CCMP1771

**Ceratium fusus,
Strain PA161109**

Chaetoceros affinis CCMP159

Karenia brevis Wilson

**Karlodinium micrum,
Strain CCMP2283**

Pseudo-nitzschia arenysensis

**Alexandrium margalefi,
Strain AMGDE01CS-322**

Thalassionema frauenfeldii

**Alexandrium catenella,
Strain OF101**

**Detonula confervacea,
Strain CCMP 353**

**Thalassiosira,
Strain NH16**

Figure S9 Percent identity histograms showing shift in distance to top 22 MMETSP references across nitrogen conditions.

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Figure S10 Percent identity histograms showing shift in distance to top 22 MMETSP references across iron conditions.

Figure S11 (A) SNV abundance (x) and percent of SNVs non-synonymous (y) for ab initio ORF LPI taxa groups. **(B)** SNV density (total SNVs/ total ORFs) for major phytoplankton taxa across incubation conditions, colored by nutrient status.

Figure S12 Mean frequency of non-synonymous alleles across (A) nitrogen and (B) iron conditions. Alleles of interest are colored by functional annotation and other alleles are shown in light grey. Allele frequency is calculated as number of reads of a given allele / number of total reads across all alleles at that position (DP). An allele frequency of 1 would indicate that the entire pool of alleles is made up of a given allele, and zero would indicate that the given allele was not measured. The dashed line is a 1:1 line. Alleles above the line are more frequent in replete conditions; alleles below the line are more frequent in deplete conditions. Functional annotation abbreviations: GAPD1 = glyceraldehyde-3-

phosphate dehydrogenase; LHC = light harvesting complex; MFS = Major Facilitator Superfamily of small compound transporters, PbgD = porphobilinogen deaminase; TKT2 = transketolase; TPI3 = triose-phosphate isomerase. Arginosuccinate synthase (ASS) is responsible for the 3rd step in the urea cycle, BCCT = betaine/carnitine/choline transporter. Points are plotted with a jitter of 0.05 for best viewing.

Figure S13 Phylogenetic tree of the viral ORF (contig_1975898_1_2441_+, red) with variants that rose to dominance late-bloom in both experiments, during diatom bloom decline. The sequence was identified as a fragment of +ssRNA polyprotein, containing a helicase domain (PF01443). Six of the top 10 blast hits are shown along with a diatom representative containing the same PFAM model (Diatom_CtenRNAV). The sequences were trimmed for the helicase domain, resulting in 813 amino acids of the Monterey Bay sequence (contig_1975898). The following sequences are plotted Brown algae RNA virus 1 (BBZ90076.1), *Plasmopara viticola* lesion associated virga-like virus 1 (QHD64722.1), Atrato Virga-like virus 6 (QHA33758), Soil-borne cereal mosaic virus (AAF18330.1), Barley aphid RNA virus 4 (BBV14754.1), *Aphis glycines* virus 3 (ASH89118.1), *Chaetoceros tenuissimus* RNA virus (CtenRNAV) (Marnavridae). Colors denote taxonomic classification categories as follows, gray unclassified at lower taxonomic levels or environmental; purple Virgaviridae (Furovirus); light purple - Virgaviridae like (unclassified Virgaviridae); blue - Dicistroviridae (Cripavirus). Bootstrap values are shown on the tree and in legend as well as tree scale for branch length.

Figure S14 Comparison of the response of select genes to nitrogen availability in taxa from the present study versus available published datasets. Heatmap is colored by \log_2FC of N-deplete versus N-replete conditions (positive= up in deplete (blue), negative = up in replete (red)). Genes were identified using KO IDs when possible, gene IDs specific to Alipanah 2015 data (1) (Phatr2), Smith 2019 data (2) (Phatr3), and Lv 2019 data (3) (D. Salina gene IDs) were occasionally used. All annotations are catalogued in SD14. For Alipanah 2015, the “48 h” and “72 h” conditions represent 48 h and 72 h of nitrogen deprivation, respectively. \log_2FC for the present study were calculated in edgeR for each taxa group independently using raw reads summed over KO annotations. For Alexander 2020 data (4), \log_2FC between N-deplete and N-replete conditions was back-calculated from \log_2FC given in supplementary datasets by subtracting $\log_2FC(N\text{-deplete}/\text{control}) - \log_2FC(N\text{-replete}/\text{control})$. For Smith 2019 data (2), edgeR was performed on raw reads with 15 minute and 45 minute NH_4 , NO_2^- and NO_3^- timepoints considered N-replete replicates and 18 hour NH_4 , NO_2^- and NO_3^- timepoints considered N-deplete replicates.

Figure S15 Comparison of the response of select genes to nitrogen availability in diatoms, haptophytes, and dinoflagellates from the present study versus available published datasets, as in Figure S23, where full gene names are given. Heatmap is colored by \log_2FC of N-deplete versus N-replete conditions (positive= up in deplete (blue), negative = up in replete (red)).

Figure S16 Comparison of the response of select genes to iron availability in taxa from the present study versus available published datasets. Heatmap is colored by \log_2FC of iron-deplete versus iron-replete conditions (positive= up in deplete (blue), negative = up in replete (red)). Genes were identified using KO IDs, which are catalogued in SD14. \log_2FC for the present study were calculated in edgeR for each taxa group independently using raw reads summed over KO annotations. For Smith 2016 (5), \log_2FC was calculated from the “Light versus Dark” RPKM ratio given in the supplementary data, and subsequently averaged by KO ID. \log_2FC from Cohen 2017 (6) and Cohen 2018 (7) supplementary data was used directly.

Figure S17 Comparison of the response of select genes to iron availability in diatoms, haptophytes, and dinoflagellates from the present study versus available published datasets, as in Figure S26, where full gene names are given. Heatmap is colored by \log_2FC of N-deplete versus N-replete conditions (positive= up in deplete (blue), negative = up in replete (red)). Heatmap is colored by \log_2FC of iron-deplete versus iron-replete conditions (positive= up in deplete (blue), negative = up in replete (red)).

Figure S18 (A) Log ratio of diatom nitrate transporter (*NRT2*; MCL cluster 351) to glutamine synthetase (*GSII*; MCL cluster 139) gene expression, averaged by genus, alongside log ratio of *NRT2:GSII* calculated from recent laboratory experiments with *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* (2, 8). **(B)** Log ratio of nitrate transporter (*NRT2*; MCL cluster 351) to glutamine synthetase (*GSII*; MCL cluster 139) gene expression, averaged by taxa group.

Figure S19 Proposed environmental gene markers of cellular (A) nitrogen and (B) iron status in diatoms. A) Log ratio of diatom nitrate transporter (*NRT2*; MCL cluster 351) to glutamine synthetase (*GSII*; MCL cluster 139) gene expression, averaged by genus. B) Log ratio of summed diatom iron starvation induced proteins (*ISIP1*, uniprot B7GA90; *ISIP2A*, uniprot B7FYL2; *ISIP2B*, uniprot B7G9B1; *ISIP3*, uniprot B7G4H8) to *thiC* (K03147) gene expression, averaged by genus.

Figure S20 (A) Expression across nutrient conditions of ORFs with best hits to viruses of major bloom players. ORFs are grouped by their putative hosts based on best hit (grey facet labels, right) and colored by their best hit annotation. **(B)** Differential expression of significantly nutrient responsive viral ORFs across nitrogen and iron conditions. Only ORFs that are significantly differentially expressed ($\text{FDR} < 0.05$) in at least one condition are included. ORFs are grouped by putative host as determined by best hit species (facet labels; grey), scaled by total library-normalized expression across all conditions, colored by hit species, and labeled with percent identity to the best hit.

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